

Nonlinear analysis of self-sustained oscillations in an annular combustor model with electroacoustic feedback

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Abstract

Self-excited pressure oscillations can occur in combustion systems due to the thermoacoustic coupling between the unsteady acoustics and flame heat release fluctuations. Usually, the knowledge of a Flame Transfer Function is used to predict the onset of thermoacoustic instabilities. However, it is also possible to take advantage of it to model a flame response and study experimentally thermoacoustic phenomena without flames. This is exploited in the present study, in which a novel annular setup for the study of thermoacoustics in annular combustors is presented. The thermoacoustic feedback is replaced by electroacoustic feedback. The pressure fluctuations, measured by a microphone, are delayed and filtered and then sent to a loudspeaker, which produces acoustic perturbations, closing the loop. Each flame model parameter can be varied in a flexible way, which allows to choose combinations of parameters that generate modal behaviours of interest in the experiments. For example, this setup can trigger on demand various configurations which exhibit multiple unstable modes, leading to diverse modal competition scenarios. This allows to assess the multi-input Describing Function method, which is used to predict the frequency and amplitude of each mode contributing to thermoacoustic oscillations, when multiple modes are linearly unstable. The experimental validation of predictions from this method, which can be somewhat cumbersome and expensive in the presence of flames, is facilitated by this setup, in which all parameters and boundary conditions are well known and the noise remains negligible. Prediction uncertainties connected to approximations intrinsic of this method when operating in the vicinity of bifurcation points are also discussed.

Keywords:

Thermoacoustic oscillations, Annular combustor, Electroacoustic feedback, Flame Multi-Input Describing Function, Nonlinear modal coupling

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1. Introduction

The need for reducing NO_x emissions from stationary gas turbine and aero-engine combustors led to the development of lean premixed combustion technology, which however often exhibits thermoacoustic instabilities. These are due to the mutual excitation of heat release rate and acoustic fluctuations, which can lead to self-sustained high amplitude pressure oscillations that may cause flame flashback or blow-off and structural damages. To avoid these unwanted phenomena, thermoacoustic oscillations need to be addressed from the early design stages. Experimental studies provide a first-hand demonstration of thermoacoustic phenomena, and aid in developing accurate prediction methods and validating simulation tools. However, in order to properly understand the impact of each parameter (e.g., linear/nonlinear flame responses, boundary conditions, geometry, noise level, mean flow intensity) on the nature and stability of thermoacoustic modes, a large number of experiments are usually needed. Considering the complexity and operational costs of industrial combustors, generic annular laboratory-scale annular configurations have been developed to investigate thermoacoustic phenomena with some flexibility [1, 2]. In particular, experiments in laboratory combustors allow to measure the linear flame response to upstream acoustic excitations, which is known as the Flame Transfer Function (FTF) [3]. Its gain and phase are generally frequency dependent, and it represents a key element for the modelling and prediction of combustion instabilities.

Knowing the flame behaviour, one can have the idea to remove the complexity associated to combustion processes by studying thermoacoustics using a surrogate system [4]. For example, in [5] an annular Rijke tube was used, in which 12 tubes, each containing an electrically heated grid, are connected to an annular chamber. The downstream end of the annular cavity had to be open, in order to allow for an axial mean flow associated to natural convection. In the case of a simple cavity, in [6, 7] thermoacoustic phenomena have been reproduced in the absence of heat sources, using an ElectroAcoustic Feedback (EAF) mechanism. In EAF experiments the pressure fluctuation signal is measured by a microphone, filtered, delayed, saturated and sent to a loudspeaker. The latter generates unsteady acoustic waves in the cavity, mimicking the effect of a flame.

In this study we present a novel setup that uses the EAF concept into the annular combustor of [5]. This results into an EAF test rig that allows for an extensive investigation of thermoacoustics in annular combustors at various conditions. This also allows to close the down-

stream end of the annulus, thus producing a reflective boundary condition, similar to that of a choked outlet usually found at the exit of actual combustors, and to perform low-noise experiments.

Appropriate modelling and theoretical analysis of experimental results are also needed for a deeper understanding of thermoacoustic phenomena [8]. Linear stability analysis has proven to be very valuable in thermoacoustics. It allows for the prediction of the frequency and the linear growth rates of the thermoacoustic modes. When only one mode is linearly unstable, the nonlinear frequency response of the flame with respect to harmonic forcing at variable amplitude can be modelled by a Flame Describing Function (FDF), i.e. a FTF that is amplitude dependent. The use of static FDFs in thermoacoustics was first introduced in [9], where the input-amplitude dependence of the frequency response gain, allows for a reasonable prediction of limit cycle amplitude and frequency, for a single linearly unstable mode. FDF analysis in thermoacoustics has been first fully exploited in [10], in which a dynamic flame response nonlinearity, for which both the gain and the phase of the nonlinear frequency response are amplitude dependent, has been determined experimentally. Accurate numerical predictions of the FDF and its use to compute the limit cycle have also been shown when dealing with Scale Resolving CFD methods [11]. Extensions of the FDF method that allow for the simultaneous oscillation of two modes have been outlined in [12] for a static nonlinearity, and in [13] for a dynamic nonlinearity. These methods allow for the prediction of the amplitude and frequency of each of the mode contributing to thermoacoustic oscillations.

The annular EAF setup introduced in this study is used to assess the accuracy of the multi-input FDF method predictions, which generalises the FDF method when multiple (up to three in our case) modes are linearly unstable. We also demonstrate that the mechanisms underlying an experimental scenario exhibiting mode competition, can be enlightened by this method. The prediction uncertainties connected to this method in the vicinity of bifurcation points are also discussed.

2. Experimental setup and modelling

The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1. It has 12 tubes opened at the bottom and connected to an annular volume, mimicking, respectively, the burners and the combustion chamber of a gas turbine. The annular duct is closed by a hard wall on the top in order to have a reflective boundary condition, acoustically similar to that of a choked outlet. No mean flow is considered.

In this study, the EAF is created only in one tube, us-

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the annular test rig and EAF between the microphone and loudspeaker.

ing a loudspeaker (Monacor KU516, 160-6500Hz) and a microphone (GRAS 40BP). The acoustic pressure signal measured by the microphone is amplified and filtered by the microphone amplifier and sent to a Real-Time Controller (RTC: dSPACE1103). The RTC input signal is modulated by a transfer function and a nonlinearity. The RTC output signal is amplified (t-Amp E4-130) and sent to the loudspeaker, generating sound in the tube. In each tube the pressure fluctuations are measured by a microphone (GRAS 40BP), and recorded by the RTC. A sampling frequency of 12 kHz is used in the RTC, both for the EAF and for the recording. The microphones have been relatively calibrated, and their voltage signals are later converted into pressure units thanks to an absolute calibration.

2.1. Acoustic response

In order to better understand the observed dynamics, we build a low-order model of our setup. To do so, we first measure its frequency response and then fit an analytical model onto it. Our system is represented by a Single Input Multiple Output system, assumed to be linear. The scalar input u is the signal sent by the RTC output, and the output vector \mathbf{y} is the collection of the signals y_i ($i = 1..12$) recorded by the RTC input channels (see Fig. 1). The system, characterised in frequency domain, thus comprises the acoustic response of the rig together

Figure 2: Comparison between the acoustic response of tube 1 measured experimentally when forcing the loudspeaker and the fitted SSM, over the range of frequencies of interest. Analogous results are obtained for the other components of the frequency response vector.

with the RTC input/output channels, the loudspeaker, the microphones, and the amplifier channels responses. We note that it would be possible to identify the frequency response of each component individually [5], but this is not necessary for the purpose of the current study. For simplicity, we shall refer to the combined frequency response of the whole experimental setup and hardware as the acoustic response.

The acoustic frequency response is measured by imposing a chirp signal at the input u , for which the frequency increases linearly over time from 160 to 750 Hz. The i^{th} component of the experimental frequency response vector in the frequency domain is then

$$\frac{\hat{y}_i(i\omega)}{\hat{u}(i\omega)} = \frac{\hat{S}_{y_i u}}{\hat{S}_{uu}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{S}_{z_1 z_2}$ is the cross power spectral density between z_1 and z_2 . As done in [14], we choose to fit a State Space Model (SSM) onto the frequency response of our system. The SSM is defined in the Laplace domain as

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(s) = \mathbf{G}(s)\hat{u}(s), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{G}(s) \equiv \mathbf{C}(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{B}$ is a 12×1 vector modelling the frequency response in each duct of the annular system. The coefficients of the matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} are determined by fitting the measured acoustic response, Eq. (1), onto the SSM (2) [15]. The model has 28 states, which is twice the number of resonant frequencies between 160 and 750 Hz. Fig. 2 validates the fitted SSM against the measured frequency response.

2.2. Linear flame response model with EAF

To mimic the response and coupling of a flame heat release rate with the acoustics, we employ EAF (see Fig. 1). The acoustic signal measured with a microphone at a reference location is first amplified by the RTC with a gain n and delayed by a characteristic time τ , then used to actuate a loudspeaker. This models the typical delayed response of flames to acoustic perturbations [16]. Furthermore, flames typically exhibit a low-pass behaviour [3]. We model this with a second order low-pass filter. The model that is used in time-domain in the EAF, to link the linear flame model output $q(t)$ to its acoustic input $y_1(t)$, can be represented in the Laplace domain by the following FTF:

$$\text{FTF}(s) \equiv \frac{\hat{q}}{\hat{y}_1} = \frac{\omega_c^2}{s^2 + 2(\omega_c \zeta)s + \omega_c^2} n e^{-s\tau}, \quad (3)$$

where $\zeta = 0.707$ is a damping coefficient and ω_c a cut-off frequency. The EAF may encode any measured FTF. In this study, however, we use the more flexible

model (3) as it allows us to emulate the response of flames exhibiting different gains, time delays and cut-off frequencies, by varying the parameters n , τ , and ω_c , respectively. In the present study, the latter is kept constant, $\omega_c/(2\pi) = 300$ Hz.

2.3. Nonlinear saturation and Describing Functions

The coupling between the acoustic response and the FTF can destabilise some eigenmodes of the system. The set of unstable modes can be found by solving the dispersion relation

$$G_1(s)\text{FTF}(s) = 1, \quad (4)$$

where G_1 is the first component of \mathbf{G} , Eq. (2), i.e. of the tube in which the EAF is located. The solutions for which the growth rate $\sigma = \Re(s)$ is positive will, in the linear regime, grow exponentially over time without interacting with each other, oscillating at a frequency $\omega = \Im(s)$. Eventually, the amplitude of the linearly unstable modes will reach values sufficiently high to trigger nonlinear saturation effects. In the nonlinear regime the oscillating modes interact with each other and saturate towards a finite amplitude steady state oscillation. A variety of models, either static (frequency independent) or dynamic (frequency dependent) has been suggested for modelling the flame nonlinear effects in time domain. In this study, we shall employ a static saturation flame model of the form [9]

$$u(q(t)) = \begin{cases} q & \text{if } |q| < \delta \\ \delta \text{sgn}(q) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (5)$$

Static nonlinearities are commonly used in thermoacoustic modelling as they can well reproduce the saturation mechanisms at specific frequencies and allow for analytical treatment of the equations [7].

A common method employed to understand flame saturation effects is the Describing Function (DF), which approximates the nonlinearity assuming that only one mode oscillates. In our experiments, however, multiple modes can be simultaneously unstable. If the oscillations contain more than one dominant frequency, it is necessary to use the multi-input DF [17]. For M dominant frequencies, the signal that enters the nonlinearity can be approximated as

$$q(t) \approx \sum_{k=1}^M a_k \sin(\omega_k t), \quad (6)$$

where a_k is the amplitude of the ω_k frequency component. In thermoacoustics, only DF with one or two inputs have been considered so far [10, 12, 13]. It is generally costly to measure a multi-input DF experimentally.

However, having at hand a static saturation as (5), the multi-input DF can be evaluated as

$$\mathcal{N}_i(\mathbf{a}) \equiv \frac{2}{(2\pi)^M a_i} \int_0^{2\pi} u\left(\sum_{k=1}^M a_k \sin(\varphi_k)\right) \sin(\varphi_i) d\Phi, \quad (7)$$

where $d\Phi \equiv \prod_{k=1}^M d\varphi_k$, $\varphi_k \equiv \omega_k t$ and $\mathbf{a} = [a_1, \dots, a_M]$. $\mathcal{N}_i(\mathbf{a})$, $i = 1..M$, contains the ratio between the amplitude of the frequency component ω_i when all M modes are oscillating simultaneously at amplitudes \mathbf{a} . This is unity for all components in the linear regime and decreases towards zero at very large amplitudes: it can therefore be used as a measure of the saturation level that every oscillating mode experiences: the lower \mathcal{N}_i , the higher the saturation level of mode i .

2.4. Harmonic balance and modal amplitude evolution

As for all dynamical systems, the instantaneous amplitudes, frequencies and growth rates of thermoacoustic modes that contribute to the dynamics vary in time until reaching a steady state oscillation pattern. Since their evolution is generally much slower than the oscillation rate of unstable thermoacoustic modes, they can be tracked by means of the harmonic balance method, which generalises Eq. (4) in the presence of M frequency components and a nonlinearity. It reads

$$G_1(s_i)\text{FTF}(s_i)\mathcal{N}_i(\mathbf{a}) = 1 \quad \text{for } i = 1..M, \quad (8)$$

and consists of M complex-valued equations that can be solved for the M complex-valued Laplace variable s_i at a given amplitude state \mathbf{a} . The equations are coupled by the nonlinear terms \mathcal{N}_i , which are function of the amplitudes of all the modes. Since for small amplitudes, $\mathcal{N}_i = 1$ for all i , Eqs. (8) are decoupled in the linear limit.

Eqs. (7) and (8) are useful per se, as they allow us to calculate the instantaneous saturation levels and variations in growth rates and frequencies of the modes contributing to the dynamics. But they can also be combined to obtain a low-order predictive time domain model for the amplitude evolution. The instantaneous variation of the amplitude of each mode is

$$\dot{a}_i = \sigma_i(\mathbf{a})a_i \quad i = 1..M, \quad (9)$$

which are again a set of equations coupled by the current amplitude levels of all modes \mathbf{a} . Starting from an initial condition \mathbf{a}_0 at time $t = 0$, the low-order model integration proceeds as follows: (i) we plug $\mathbf{a}(t)$ into Eq. (7) and calculate the values of the multi-input DF at the current amplitude state; (ii) we use the calculated values of \mathcal{N}_i into Eq. (8), solving for the instantaneous

growth rates (σ_i) and frequencies (ω_i) of all modes; (iii) we integrate one step forward in time Eq. (9), obtaining the updated amplitude levels at the next time step; (iv) we repeat from (i) until the desired time. This method is faster than the calculation of the entire multi-input DF, as in [12], as it requires solving Eqs. (7) and (8) at the amplitude levels reached by the modes only.

3. Experimental results and model-based analysis

Experiments have been performed using values of n , τ and δ for which the dispersion relation (4) predicts multiple modes with positive linear growth rates. The method presented in §2.4 is applied to understand the dynamical route towards the final state and the nonlinear modal coupling observed in the experiments.

Time resolved saturation and coupling mechanisms in a thermoacoustic system with multiple unstable modes

The flame model parameters are set to $n = 0.15$, $\tau = 0.75$ ms, $\delta = 0.4$ V. Linear analysis predicts three unstable modes, with growth rates $\sigma_m = [30, 13, 26]$ s⁻¹ and frequencies $f_m = [480, 445, 498]$ Hz. We label the modes by their dominant azimuthal order, which is $m = [2, 3, 4]$ respectively. The evolution of the amplitudes of these modes, obtained from the experiment and the low-order model, are shown in Fig. 3. These amplitudes are directly calculated by the latter method, and are extracted from peaks in the spectrograms of the time series of the experiment recorded in tube 1. The non-dimensional amplitudes a_m calculated with the low-order model are scaled to pressure values with appropriate factors that can be determined from the feedback loop shown in Fig. 1. In the experiment, mode $m = 2$, which has the highest linear growth rate, initially grows

Figure 3: Time evolution of the amplitudes of the unstable modes from experiments (top) and low-order model (bottom). Mode $m = 2$ has the largest growth rate in the linear regime, but when nonlinear effects start it is strongly damped, and it is mode $m = 4$ that dominates the steady state dynamics.

to high amplitudes faster than all other modes, but eventually decays, giving way to the growth of another mode ($m = 4$). Mode $m = 3$ is also always observed to grow and then decay, but never reaches significant amplitudes. The same quantitative trend is found in the low-order model. These results suggest that it's not always true that the dominant mode is the one with the largest growth rate as often assumed in common investigations. This somewhat counter-intuitive observation was first discussed in [12], and it is one of our goals to give some insights on its occurrence. The low-order model based on the multi-input DF helps in this respect. First, we note that the possible solutions of the thermoacoustic system, identified by finding the equilibria of Eq. (9) are three: a fixed-point (with all amplitudes vanishing), and two limit cycles (one with only a_2 active and one with only a_4 active). They are shown in Fig. 4 (left), which contains a 2D projection of the 3D phase space, with $a_3 = 0$. Their stability is determined by means of the criteria discussed in [13]. The fixed point solution was already known to be unstable from linear analysis. The limit cycle with $a_2 > 0$ is unstable, having $d\sigma_2/dA_2 < 0$ but $\sigma_4 > 0$. This means that when mode 2 has saturated to finite amplitude, the one of mode 4 will instead grow further. The limit cycle with $a_4 > 0$ is the only stable solution, having $\sigma_2 < 0$ and $d\sigma_4/dA_4 < 0$. This prediction is verified by performing the experiment at the same conditions.

When multiple thermoacoustic modes are linearly unstable and grow in amplitude, the nonlinear coupling between the modes determines the saturation mechanisms and the stability of the equilibria. This information can be visualised by calculating the saturation map

Figure 4: Phase space (left) and multi-input DF maps for the modes a_2 and a_4 . The trajectory followed by these amplitudes as per Fig. (3) is shown on the plane $a_3 = 0$. The markers on the trajectory indicate the transition between the regions discussed in Fig. 5

of each mode, from Eq. (7). Figs. 4 (middle and right) shows how modes 2 and 4 are saturated, on the $a_3 = 0$ plane only for ease of representation and as a_3 never reaches high amplitudes. The saturation maps \mathcal{N}_i are used to calculate growth rate (and frequency) maps by solving (8). The product between the instantaneous amplitude and the growth rate of each mode is finally computed and shown in the vector field of Fig. 4a. At any given point, this vector field is tangent to the trajectory followed by the modal amplitudes. Then, for a given set of initial amplitudes, this vector map can be intuitively used to track the temporal evolution of the modal amplitudes. The vector map confirms the stable/unstable nature of the various equilibria, and that, at this operating conditions, the dynamics should always tend to a limit cycle oscillation of the $m = 4$ mode regardless of the initial conditions. This discussion links the instantaneous modal amplitudes, saturation levels and growth rates in a qualitative way. A more quantitative analysis can be performed by tracking the conjoint temporal evolution of the amplitude, growth rate and multi-input DF components \mathcal{N}_i of all the modes contributing to the dynamics. These quantities are shown in Fig. 5, and help separating the dynamics into various stages. We identify a linear regime (A), during which the total amplitude is lower than δ and each amplitude grows exponentially at the identified rates. In a first transient region, (B), the total amplitude exceeds δ and nonlinear effects start. All nonlinear gains – particularly those of modes 3 and 4, $\mathcal{N}_{3/4}$, whose amplitude are still small – drop quickly.

This causes the growth rates of all three modes to de-

Figure 5: Temporal evolution of the amplitudes, growth rates and multi-input DF components (\mathcal{N}_i) of all the 3 unstable thermoacoustic modes.

crease: the one of mode 2 approaches zero, the one of mode 3 becomes negative, but the one of mode 4 remains slightly positive. The latter causes the existence of another quasi-linear region, (C), in which mode 3 does no longer participate to the dynamics (its amplitude drops), mode 2 is neutrally stable (its amplitude remains constant), but the amplitude of mode 4 grows exponentially at a reduced, roughly constant, growth rate. Eventually, the amplitude of mode 4 becomes comparable with that of mode 2, triggering strong modal coupling effects – which as a rule of thumb are proportional to the products of modal amplitudes. These are evident in region (D), in which energy transfer between the modes makes the saturation level of mode 2 to suddenly drop to very low values. This causes its growth rate to decrease, which becomes negative and leads to a full decay of its modal amplitude. In the steady state, (E), only mode 4 has survived, and its stability is confirmed by the fact that its own growth rate has vanished, whereas that of the other modes is negative.

This case demonstrates that our setup allows to mimic thermoacoustic instabilities and their nonlinear saturation. The flexibility in the flame model parameters characteristic of the EAF makes it possible to investigate behaviours of interest, which can be predicted by using the multi-input DF method presented in §2.4.

Prediction uncertainties close to bifurcation points

The flame model parameters are now changed to $n = 0.04$, $\tau = 2.5$ ms and $\delta=0.5$ V. Linear analysis predicts two unstable modes, whose growth rates and frequencies are $\sigma_m = [1.61, 1.62]$ s⁻¹ and $f_m = [514, 528]$ Hz, with dominant azimuthal mode number $m = [4, 5]$ respectively. Contrary to the previous scenario, by solving for the equilibria of Eq. (9) and their stability with the current set of parameters, we predict that two stable equilibrium solutions exist. They correspond to independent periodic oscillations of mode 4 or mode 5. On top of them, two unstable solutions are found: the fixed point solution known to be unstable from linear stability analysis, and a mixed-mode solution, with $a_5 = 0.34$ and $a_4 = 0.34$. This solution can be shown to be a saddle point by using the stability criteria reported in [13]. All solutions are shown in Fig. 6a.

The experimental results, shown with a solid line in Fig. 6, do not show any contribution from mode 5, even in the linear regime. Although the final amplitude of the oscillation is well-predicted by the method, the complete absence of mode 5 in the linear regime is in conflict with the theoretical prediction. However, it can be noticed that the predicted growth rates are small. It is therefore likely that a small variation of

Figure 6: Phase spaces of $m = 4, 5$ amplitude evolution across a bifurcation. The bifurcation is found at $n \approx 0.0365$ and makes mode 5 linearly stable, making its limit cycle solution disappear. The trajectory identified in the experiment with $n = 0.04$ is plotted with a black line in both graphs.

any of the flame model parameters makes the growth rate of at least one of these modes negative. This is tested by performing a frequency domain analysis with a slightly lower gain. By reducing the flame model gain to $n = 0.036$, the resolution of the dispersion relation (4) predicts that mode 5 becomes linearly stable with $\sigma_5 = -0.40 \text{ s}^{-1}$, while mode 4 remains linearly unstable with $\sigma_4 = 0.04 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The change in the linear stability caused by slightly decreasing the gain demonstrates the presence of a bifurcation between these values, in the vicinity of $n = 0.0365$.

Then, a nonlinear analysis by means of the multi-input DF method shows that only one stable equilibrium solution exists, shown in Fig. 6b, corresponding to a periodic oscillation of mode 4. Although the trajectory identified in the experiment fits better the phase space identified for $n = 0.036$ than that identified for $n = 0.04$, the final amplitude of the oscillation is underestimated in this case. It is therefore likely that the experimental results correspond to a phase-space behaviour which lies in between those shown in Fig. 6. Since the flame model parameters are imposed to be the same for the experimental and theoretical analysis, this cannot be the cause of the mismatch. We therefore attribute the predictive uncertainty to errors in the fitted acoustic model. In fact, although the fitting shown in Fig. (2) is accurate, it is not free of errors. Close inspection shows that the gain of the fitted model around the frequency of mode 5 overshoots the measured gain by approximately 2%. Therefore, a lower flame model gain value needs to be used to accurately reproduce the closed-loop gain

at experimental conditions, consistently with our observations. This uncertainty is small, and generally not so relevant for amplitude/frequency predictions. However, close to a bifurcation, at which the predicted behaviour can suddenly change, the prediction accuracy is extremely sensitive to the acoustic model uncertainties.

4. Conclusions

A novel setup developed to study thermoacoustic phenomena in annular combustors using EAF is presented in this article. A state space model is fitted onto the experimentally determined acoustic response of the test rig, and used to perform a frequency domain analysis for multiple sets of flame model parameters and identify conditions of interest for experimental analysis of thermoacoustic oscillations. The flame response is represented by a delayed, low-pass filter flexible model, although it may be chosen to be an experimentally measured FTF. Two cases for which linear analysis predicts multiple linearly unstable modes are identified and investigated experimentally. The measurements are compared with theoretical predictions from the multi-input DF method, whose accuracy can be thoroughly tested with our setup.

In the first case, the modal competition scenario observed in the experiment is well predicted and explained by the multi-input DF method. The key role in the nonlinear dynamical behaviour of the saturation level of each mode is quantified by means of the multi-input DF method. We show how the time evolution of the saturation level of each mode is controlled by the dynamics of all amplitudes, and that it drives the evolution of the respective growth rate. The latter, in turn, governs the variation of the amplitude of the associated mode. We demonstrate how nonlinear modal coupling can lead to a complete suppression of the mode with the largest linear growth rate in the steady state regime.

In the second case, the prediction uncertainties are discussed. We show that small uncertainties contained in the fitted acoustic state space model propagate into the prediction of the dynamics. Although small, these uncertainties can lead to radical differences between the observed and predicted behaviours when operating in the proximity of a bifurcation point, around which the accuracy of any predictive method is very sensitive to small uncertainties in the system parameters.

These scenarios demonstrate the flexibility of the EAF annular setup and its ability to mimic instabilities and oscillation behaviours analogous to those of thermoacoustic phenomena. The assessment of the multi-input DF method performed here was done in noise-free conditions, as the latter is negligible in EAF exper-

iments, and allows the system to evolve in a deterministic manner towards a well defined final state. Thus, our setup is suitable for the validation of deterministic prediction methods. It can however be easily modified also for the investigation of, e.g., the effect of stochastic forcing, presence of an azimuthal mean flow, and flame response staging.

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